

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: Mulae****FIRST NAME: Julius****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: P1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: MSWord for Mac Version 16.43 on macOS Big Sur Version 11.0.1

7 key concepts with the page number in the text (Grammarly reported Plagiarism rate 6%)

1. Basics of sound academic writing (EUCLID 2019, 1-4)
2. Avoiding the pitfalls of Plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5-13)
3. Personal versus academic style (EUCLID 2019, 12)
4. Basics of grammar and structure (EUCLID 2019, 17-23)
5. American versus British English (EUCLID 2019, 27-35)
6. Chicago style (EUCLID 2019, 44-45)
7. Appropriate usage of Latin abbreviations (EUCLID 2019, 54-62)

ACADEMIC WRITING AN INTRODUCTION

1) INTRODUCTION

In my private and professional life, writing text messages, emails, and business reports is a daily requirement. Still, until now I have not paid too much attention to the variations and different conditions for writing styles (EUCLID 2019, 24) until I commenced reviewing and analyzing the reading requirements for the ACA-401D. It appears that I will need to master the persuasive writing style for my academic papers to convince my readers of my position using my arguments and reasoning. Additionally, I will seek to apply others' research and their ideas while giving them full credit to avoid plagiarism.

While there is some debate about what academic style exactly is, my main take away from the review of ACA-401D Coursepack for period one (1) is the dos and don'ts of academic writing (EUCLID 2019, 17) of which there is general agreement.

The application of modern software tools such as Grammarly and Zotero enables referencing and citation consistently. I spend considerable time and effort learning how to apply the tools effectively. I found the ACA-401D coursepack for period one (1) and the associated instructional EUCLID YouTube video particularly helpful in guiding how to use the tools effectively.

2) AVOIDING THE PITFALLS OF PLAGIARISM

The Cambridge English Dictionary defines plagiarism as the process or practice of using another person's ideas or work and pretending to be your own. Another definition is plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information (EUCLID 2019, 4). In academic writing, it is essential to cite all ideas or work of others used correctly. Students must ensure that all quotations and paraphrases are appropriately noted. EUCLID recommends the Chicago Rules (Turabian) and also the use of American English (EUCLID 2019, 24), but other versions are also accepted.

Plagiarism in academic writing is wrong and unethical (EUCLID 2019) and is to be avoided. It is not always easy to balance personal ideas and those of others to be cited. EUCLID provides Grammarly as a tool to help students check work before submission for plagiarism. In an office setting, especially in transnational commercial organizations where branding is essential, my direct experience is that copy and paste of specific phrases, wording and graphics when preparing internal company documentation is typical and often expected. In academic writing, this is a hazard that must be carefully managed. The key to successful academic writing being to master citation styles and when to apply them.

3) PERSONAL VERSUS ACADEMIC WRITING STYLE

A critical difference between the personal style and academic writing style is that academic writing has particular rules, including a requirement for citation (EUCLID 2019, 12). Personal writing style can be more relaxed and unique, especially with slang, abbreviations and contractions. Personal writing style can be very personalized and directly reflect how an individual would, for example, portray themselves on social media.

On the other hand, the academic writing style has definite dos and don'ts underpinned by the choice of specific rules to follow, for example, for EUCLID, the rule of style for in-text citations.

Some key things to exclude are slang, contractions, sweeping generalizations, making assumptions, giving opinions, everyday vocabulary and some of the things to include are correct grammar, use of full verb forms, formal language, right spelling, and punctuation (EUCLID 2019, 5-13).

4) BASICS OF GRAMMAR AND STRUCTURE

As indicated above, an essential requirement of academic writing is the use of correct grammar and punctuation. Modern software such as Grammarly or Microsoft Word is indispensable in checking spellings and elements of structure in an essay, but the underlying basic grammar requires a good understanding of the basics of spelling and grammar as covered in (EUCLID 2019, 17-23; Parkinson 2011, 9-19).

While revising the apostrophe's proper use when indicating possession, using “it’s” and “its” and other critical elements of grammar and punctuation, I could not help but reflect on social media's impact. Texting, Facebook, and other social media language abbreviations and contractions in writing have a distinct effect on the day-to-day English language usage and writing.

5) AMERICAN VERSUS BRITISH ENGLISH

Since the end of the second world war American English due to America’s political, economic, technological, and cultural influences (EUCLID 2019), has grown steadily. I will use and follow standard American English for spelling and punctuation in this initial response paper to recognize the above.

The differences between standard American English (SAE) and standard British English (SBE) should not be underestimated. A few years ago, when on assignment to a US project with both British and American team members, one of the most useful tools we quickly devised was a large board in the shared project room. The team collectively wrote down all possible SAE and SBE differences we could think of or come across as part of our daily interactions for quick reference. The board become one of the most visited reference points. It added real value to knowledge and facilitated communication by supporting the understanding of pronunciation, spelling, and the meaning of English words and expressions used in the UK and the USA.

On a radio broadcast on BBC Culture in September 2017, “Is American English Killing British English,” Anderson Hephzibah argues that many original British English words and phrases are being replaced and that British English is not holding up well to the Americanized alternatives. Abbreviations, everyday language, shorthand social media acronyms such as “OMG” or “LOL” have given American English an advantage over British English. Quoting research, he states that:

Speaking on the wireless in 1935, Alistair Cooke declared that “Every Englishman listening to me now unconsciously uses 30 or 40 Americanisms a day.” In 2017, that number is likely closer to three or four hundred (Anderson Hephzibah 2017).

The trend appears to be that the original British English is dying a slow death. For this course, spelling checker software and specialist dictionaries will be beneficial and be relied on to apply the chosen American English. However, the usage of abbreviations, dates formats, and punctuation (EUCLID 2019) is a key takeaway that I will need to master when applying the American style.

6) CHICAGO STYLE

In the Chicago Manual of Style, an in-text citation has the author’s publication year and a page number. Additionally, each in-text citation must correspond to an entry in the

reference list (EUCLID 2019, 44). Turabian is a version of Chicago Style, and EUCLID recommends applying this style as it is aimed at students and researchers.

The Chicago Manual of Style Online (<https://www.chicagomanualofstyle.org/home.html>) provides quick and convenient access to the two systems of Notes and Bibliography or Author-Date. The Author-Date is more common in the sciences, including social sciences, while the Notes and Bibliography are preferred in humanities. The online resources are easy to access and cover many examples of both systems that are very similar apart from the numbered notes instead of the in-text parenthetical references.

7) APPROPRIATE USAGE OF LATIN ABBREVIATION

I can recall from my very early days of primary school education using abbreviations such as “A.D.” or “e.g.,” without appreciating the Latin origins or their meaning. For academic writing, primarily scientific papers, the use of Latin abbreviations is typical and expected, and used as per convention, including lower case and period, needs to be applied strictly; otherwise, it would amount to a misspelling of the abbreviation (EUCLID 2019).

Application of plain language when creating content is desirable as this ensures that miscommunication due to jargon, acronyms, and abbreviations is minimized (EUCLID 2019). Latin abbreviations however, in the right context can be and should be used as appropriate communication tools.

8) CONCLUSION

The coursepack for ACA-401D period one (1), the orientation documentation, including the recommended videos provided by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma, gave me a very detailed introduction to studying at EUCLID and set the expectations for future periods. I spend a significant period setting up the required study materials and familiarizing myself with the essential software for this current period and future periods.

Reviewing the course pack materials and the related reading was an excellent opportunity to revise basic grammar and writing styles. My journey to master academic writing has started, and I will endeavor to treat each course and period in the EUCLID syllabus as an opportunity to learn and master something new.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd ed. 2019. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University.

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. 2020. *How to Write a Response Paper*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University.

Hepzibah, Anderson. 2017. "How Americanisms Are Killing the English Language." <https://www.bbc.com/culture/article/20170904-how-americanisms-are-killing-the-english-language>.

Parkinson, Judy. 2011. *I Before E (Except After C): Old-School Ways to Remember Stuff*. London: Michael O' Mara Books.

The University of Chicago Press. *The Chicago Manual of Style Online*. https://www.chicagomanualofstyle.org/tools_citationguide.html(accessed November 27, 2020).

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.